

INVESTIGATIONS ON HYPONITRATES. PART I. SODIUM AND POTASSIUM HYPONITRATES

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Sodium and potassium hyponitrates have been prepared successfully and their chemical reactions studied.

Although hyponitric acid ($\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$) called nitrohydroxylaminic acid by Angeli (*Gazzetta*; 1896 26, *ii*, 17_s) and its salts (nitrohydroxylaminates) are known to exist, there is not much information available on their properties.

The sodium and potassium hyponitrates required for the present work were prepared by a modification of the method used by Angelico and Fanara (*Gazzetta*, 1901 31, *ii*, 21). The potassium salt gives well defined and large crystals and is more hygroscopic than the sodium salt, but is always contaminated with considerable quantities of nitrite and nitrate. The above workers obtained it as $\text{K}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, while our results show it to be $\text{K}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Action of Air, Saturated Aqueous Vapour, and Dry Carbon Dioxide.—Angeli and co-workers (*ibid.* 1900 30, 593) found that when sodium hyponitrate is exposed to air, rapid absorption of oxygen takes place forming sodium nitrite, which in presence of excess of hyponitrate partially undergoes further oxidation to nitrate. We have found that if sodium hyponitrate is exposed to air, it rapidly absorbs moisture and increases in weight. After a certain time (about seven days), it begins to lose weight. If it is exposed to water vapour in a desiccator containing water, the increase in weight continues for a considerable time, but the weight immediately begins to fall on exposure to free air. If the dry salt is exposed to dry carbon dioxide (over sulphuric acid) in a desiccator, the weight remains unchanged. A sample exposed in this manner for about a fortnight, was found to undergo negligible change in weight. It gave with silver nitrate solution a black precipitate, characteristic of hyponitrates, whereas that salt after exposure to air or water vapour did not give this test, showing the absence of hyponitrate in the latter. If a sample of sodium hyponitrate is exposed to *dry* air instead of moist or ordinary air the salt does undergo the same changes but the rate of decomposition is very slow.

It appears that the dry salt is unaffected by carbon dioxide and is hygroscopic but in contact with water vapour or in solution, it is slowly decomposed into nitrite, nitrate, and carbonate.

Action of Water.—An aqueous solution of sodium hyponitrate decomposes on standing forming nitrite with the liberation nitrous oxide

This agrees with the observation of Angeli (*loc. cit.*) who suggested the following equation for aqueous decomposition of hyponitric acid

Action of Alkalies.—Previous investigators do not seem to have studied the influence of alkalies on hyponitrates. The rate of decomposition of aqueous solutions of hyponitrates, according to the equation already given, was considerably reduced on addition of 5*N* (approx.) solution of sodium hydroxide. It therefore appears that alkalies have a stabilising influence on hyponitrates; this may be explained by supposing that hyponitric acid being a weak acid, its salts are considerably hydrolysed in solution:

and the addition of alkali decreases the concentration of the free acid.

Action of Acids.—In presence of dilute acids, hyponitric acid decomposes according to the equation (2), given, above for aqueous solutions; as the concentration of the acid is increased, a greater portion of the salt decomposes according to the equation given by Angeli and Angelico (*loc. cit.*)

Oxidation with Potassium Permanganate.—Oxidation of hyponitrates by means of potassium permanganate in neutral solution was found by Angeli (*Gazzetta*, 1904 34, i, 50) to take place nearly quantitatively according to the equation

We find that the amount of permanganate required for oxidation depends largely upon experimental conditions. In presence of alkalies and in neutral solutions, a very small amount of permanganate is absorbed. The oxidation of hyponitrate to nitrate is maximum when concentrated sulphuric acid is added fifteen minutes after the permanganate is mixed with the solution of the salt. In other cases, the amount of permanganate required after the addition of acid depends upon the dilution as well as upon the nature of the acid in presence of which the oxidation is carried out. In the case of acetic acid and hydrochloric acid, the amount of permanganate consumed was considerably high probably due to the interaction of these reagents themselves with potassium permanganate. The low values obtained in certain cases may be attributed to the fact that a portion of the hyponitric acid is simultaneously decomposed according to the equation (2) above.

Reduction.—Previous investigators do not seem to have studied the action of reducing agents on hyponitrates. Among the products of reduction of hyponitric acid, the most likely to be formed are nitrogen, hydroxylamine, hydrazine, and ammonia. By reduction with Devarda's alloy and caustic potash, stannous chloride, sodium hydrosulphite, and zinc and acetic acid, we find that none of the first three are formed, and so far, none of the above reducing agents have been found to effect a quantitative reduction of the hyponitrates.

Thermal Decomposition.—On heating sodium hyponitrate to incipient fusion, Angeli (*loc. cit.*) obtained sodium nitrite and hyponitrite :

We have further examined the products of this thermal decomposition and found that the reaction cannot be represented by one equation and the hyponitrite formed further decomposes according to the following equation

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Sodium Hyponitrate.—Pieces of clean, freshly cut sodium metal (5g., weighed under kerosene to avoid possible formation of its oxide) were dissolved by dropping each piece in 15.0 c.c. of methyl alcohol after it was rapidly pressed between folds of filter paper. A [solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was prepared by dissolving 5.0 g. of the salt, previously dried over calcium chloride, in a minimum quantity of methyl alcohol. The alcohol was thoroughly dried for seven days over calcium oxide and subsequently distilled over metallic sodium, the last and the first distillates being rejected. Each of these solutions was cooled in ice-cold water. They were then slowly mixed, shaken and left for fifteen minutes in a freezing mixture. The precipitate of sodium chloride formed was filtered off. To the clear filtrate were added 25.0 c.c. of a 40% methyl alcoholic solution of methyl nitrate, and the mixture was vigorously shaken and left for four hours in a bath of ice-cold water to ensure the completion of the reaction. A white amorphous precipitate of sodium hyponitrate, which was formed, was filtered on a Gooch crucible, washed several times with methyl alcohol and finally with ether, dried and weighed. (Found : N, 22.56 ; Na, 37.60. Calc. N, 22.95 ; Na, 37.70 per cent).

Potassium Hyponitrate.—Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (7.0 g.) was dissolved in 25.0 c.c. of methyl alcohol. To this was added a solution of 16.8 g. of potassium hydroxide in 25.0 c.c. of methyl alcohol. The details of further procedure are the same as in the case of sodium hyponitrate (Found : N, 16.01 ; K, 45.11 ; H, 11.10. Calc. N, 16.28 ; K, 45.35 ; H₂O, 10.47 per cent).

TABLE I

Hyponitrates after exposure under different conditions.

Salt.	Exposed to air for four weeks.		
		Exposed to air, sat. with aq. vapour, for four weeks.	
Na hyponitrate	NaNO ₂	68.44%	69.00%
	Na ₂ CO ₃	30.67	20.50
	NaHCO ₃	1.11	9.45
	Nitrate	Traces	Traces.
K hyponitrate	K ₂ CO ₃	11.00	11.54
	KNO ₂	34.29	72.55
	KNO ₃	54.32	16.00

TABLE II

The rate of decomposition of hyponitrates by cold water (room temp. 30°).

0.05M solution of Na-hyponitrate = 10.0 c.c.		0.05M solution of K-hyponitrate = 10.0 cc.	
Time.	KMnO ₄ soln. (0.1N) absorbed. 29.8 c.c.	Time.	KMnO ₄ soln. (0.1N) absorbed. 18.6 c.c.
0		0	
4 days.	27.8	1	14.0
7	19.6	2 days.	12.1
10	14.4	4	10.1
13	12.0	5	10.0
15	11.0	6	10.0
18	10.4	7	10.0
21	10.0	10	10.0
24	10.0	13	10.0
28	10.0	15	10.0

TABLE III

Decomposition of Na and K hyponitrates by acids.

Salt.	Acid used.	Amount of salt taken.	NO evolved at N. T. P.	N ₂ in salt as NO.	N ₂ as NO in the salt (average)	N ₂ as nitrite in salt.	N ₂ as nitrate in salt.	Total N ₂ calc. N ₂ in the salt. formula.
Na ₂ N ₂ O ₃	HCl	0.0600%	17.77 c.c.	18.51%				
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.0999	29.20	18.27	18.34%	4.57%	0.53%	23.44% 22.95%
	CH ₃ COOH	0.0820	23.92	18.24				
K ₂ N ₂ O ₃ H ₂ O	HCl	0.061	9.78	9.84				
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.0520	8.27	9.94	9.91	2.20	3.90	16.01 16.28
	CH ₃ COOH	0.0750	11.94	9.95				

TABLE IV

Oxidation with potassium permanganate.

	Na-hyponitrate		K-hyponitrate		
	Equiv. KMnO ₄ (0.1N) soln. reqd. by 1.0g. of salt.	Equiv. of O ₂ reqd.	Equiv. of KMnO ₄ (0.1N) reqd. by 1.0g. of the salt.	Equiv. of O ₂ reqd.	
No acid was added ...	...	344.2 cc.	4.20	241.9 c.c.	4.16
Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ (10.0 c.) immediately after adding solution ...	immedi- ately KMnO ₄	436.0	5.32	178.0	3.06
Do added 15 min. after adding KMnO ₄ soln. ...	...	465.4	5.68	241.9	4.16
Nitric acid—Do ...	...	416.4	5.08	201.2	3.46
Acetic acid—Do ...	...	500.0	6.1	281.4	4.81

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